

RELAY INTERPRETATION AND INDIRECT TRANSLATION: MUST-HAVES, NOT NICE-TO-HAVE

Li Zhengren

Shanghai International Studies University

Email: zhengrenli@outlook.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19332515>

Relay interpretation and indirect translation, despite the inherent issues of precision or even localization, are going to remain a fact of life. A relay example of the six UN languages will be presented, re-enforced with real life stories of human rights missions worldwide. Trump could talk to Modi only through an English interpreter repeating the Indian interpreter working from Hindi into English.

Given the issues associated with fidelity and completeness, there is apparently room for relay interpretation or indirect translation to improve. International organizations all have programs on continuous learning and MTI programs in China and elsewhere are encouraging students to add languages.